

Acoustical and thermodynamical parameters of aluminium oxide nanoparticles dispersed in aqueous hexylene glycol

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Abstract : In the present investigation aluminium oxide (Al_2O_3) nanoparticles were synthesised by precipitation method using AlCl_3 as a starting material. The synthesised nanoparticles were characterised by X-ray diffraction (XRD), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX). These nanoparticles have been dispersed in base fluid, an aqueous solution of hexylene glycol. Density (ρ), ultrasonic velocity (u) and viscosity (η) for these nanofluids have been measured at different concentrations as a function of temperatures ($T = 303.15 \text{ K}$, 308.15 K and 313.15 K). Using their values various acoustical and thermodynamical parameters have been determined.

Keywords : Al_2O_3 nanoparticles, base fluid, nanofluid, ultrasonic velocity, density, viscosity, acoustical parameters.

Introduction

This century has witnessed a tremendous escalation in the field of science and technology, for which the contribution of nanotechnology is much substantial. In the past decade, nanoscale research has opened revolutionary opportunities for a wide number of technological applications. Due to their special optical, magnetic, electrical and catalytic properties and improved physical properties like mechanical hardness, thermal stability or chemical passivity¹, metal oxide nanostructures are extensively used as paint pigments, cosmetics, pharmaceuticals, medical diagnostics, catalysts and supports, membranes and filters, batteries and fuel cells, electronics, magnetic and optical devices, flat panel displays, biomaterials, structured materials and protective coatings². Industrial demands for high performance heat exchanger devices are increasing rapidly day by day. The poor physical properties of the conventional heat transfer fluids are the major problems in improving the performance of engineering equipment. The limited heat transfer capabilities of conventional heat transfer liquids such as water, ethylene glycol (EG), propylene glycol or engine oil have been overcome by the pioneer work of Ahuja³ whereby the high thermal conductivity micro/millimeter-sized particles were suspended in the liquids. Heat transfer fluids containing sus-

pending particles of micro/millimeter sizes have numerous drawbacks like sedimentation, erosion, fouling and increased pressure drop of the flow channel. Hence, they were not accepted as suitable material for next generation heat transfer medium. The recent advances in the material science have made it possible to produce nanometer-sized particles that can overcome such problems. Innovative heat transfer fluids-suspended by nanometer-sized solid particles are called 'nanofluids'. Nanofluids are the new generation heat transfer fluids for various industrial and automotive applications because of their excellent thermal performance⁴. The main idea of dispersing solid nanoparticle in the base liquid has coined in 1995 by Choi⁵ at Argonne National Laboratory, USA which showed that the conventional liquid thermal performance could be remarkably improved using nanoparticles. Subsequent numerous investigations⁶⁻⁸ have shown that the nanofluids exhibited high thermal conductivity even for low concentrations of suspended nanoparticles. Nanofluids can be used for a wide variety of engineering applications like transportation, electronics, medical, food, defense, nuclear, space, and manufacturing of many types⁹. Magnetic nanoparticles in bio-fluids can be used for medical applications as drug delivery vehicles, providing new cancer treatment technique. Using nanofluids in heat trans-

fer applications will provide numerous other benefits including miniaturized heat exchangers, improved heat transfer, reduced heat transfer fluid inventory and reduced emissions. Use of nanofluids will conserve energy by reducing the necessary pumping power. These benefits make nanofluids a future generation heat transfer fluid. The suspended metallic and non-metallic nanoparticles can change the transport and thermal properties of the base liquid. Among the transport properties, thermal conductivity and viscosity are the fundamental characteristics of fluid that influence the heat transfer phenomena. Recently some new issues have been introduced in literatures like thermal diffusion coefficient of nanofluid¹⁰, slip mechanisms in nanofluids¹¹, electrical conductivity of nanofluids¹², nanofluids for cooling of electronic devices¹³.

This paper is devoted to the systematic experimental study on the response of suspensions of nano Al₂O₃ particles in 10% aqueous solution of hexylene glycol to the ultrasonic wave propagation. Preparing the stable and homogeneous suspensions of nanoparticles and attaining a deeper understanding of particle-fluid interaction are the main concern.

Experimental

Synthesis of nanoparticles :

Nanosized Al₂O₃ particles required for the preparation of nanofluids were synthesized in our laboratory through chemical routes¹⁴. Aluminium chloride was dissolved in aqueous media to obtain a 0.2 M concentration of transparent solution. Then 20 ml of ammonia solution was added as a precipitating agent and the pH of the solution measured before and after the addition of ammonia solution was found to be 2 and 9, respectively. The possible chemical reaction involved in the process is described by

The slurry, after repeated wash with distilled water and acetone, was filtered. The filtrate was dried in the oven at 80 °C, was made into fine powder and then annealed at 1200 °C for 2 h to obtain nanopowder of Al₂O₃. The possible chemical reaction involved in the process is described by

Preparation of nanofluids :

The nanopowder of Al₂O₃ thus obtained was dispersed

in base fluid, an aqueous solution of hexylene glycol, to obtain nanofluids of different concentrations. The nanoparticles powder weight was determined using a Mettler Toledo balance. To achieve uniform dispersion of the particles ultrasonic wave of frequency 4 MHz was passed through the fluid for 2 h with the help of ultrasonicator. It is evident that the ultrasonic treatment to the fluids increases the settling time of the suspension.

An ultrasonic interferometer provided by Mittal Enterprises, New Delhi was used to evaluate ultrasonic velocity of nanofluids. Ultrasonic velocity was measured at a frequency of 5 MHz. Viscosity was measured by using Ostwald's viscometer. The density of various nanofluids was measured with Anton Paar DSA 5000 M, Austria. All these measurements were performed for the nanofluids of different concentrations at three different temperatures 303.15 K, 308.15 K and 313.15 K.

Results and discussion

Characterization :

The synthesised nanoparticles were characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD), TEM, SEM and EDX. In the present study, Bruker AXS D8 Advance X-ray diffractometer was used to obtain X-ray diffraction patterns of the samples. The XRD pattern of synthesised nanoparticles is depicted in Fig. 1.

All diffraction peaks can be indexed as orthorhombic crystal structure of δ Al₂O₃ (space group P4m2) by comparison with data from JCPDS file no. 46-1215 with lattice constants $a = 7.93 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 37.95 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 11.71 \text{ \AA}$ and $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 90^\circ$ no characteristic peaks of any other impurity was observed. All the diffraction peaks exhibit a high degree of broadness due to the fine nature and a less degeneracy in the crystallites. Debye-Scherrer equation was used for calculating the crystallite size. The crystallite size corresponding to most intense peak was found to be 4.942 nm corresponding to 2θ value of 67.1464 and hkl (400). JEOL JEM-2100 LaB6 was used for TEM studies. TEM micrograph of the synthesised nanoparticles is depicted in Fig. 2. Average diameter of the nanoparticles was 10–14 nm evaluated by ImageJ software.

To examine the morphology of the synthesized nanoparticles, SEM analysis was carried out on the JEOL

Fig. 1. XRD pattern of Al₂O₃ nanoparticles.

Fig. 2. TEM micrograph of Al₂O₃ nanoparticles.

Fig. 3. SEM image of Al₂O₃ nanoparticles.

JSM-6390LV SEM fitted with secondary electron detector, and equipped with an attachment for the energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) to enable elemental composition analysis. SEM and EDX of the synthesised nanoparticles are depicted in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 respectively. The stoichiometry of sample was examined by EDAX spectrum. Only Al and O signals have been detected, suggesting that the nanoparticles were only made up of Al and O.

The acoustical parameters such as adiabatic compressibility (β_{ad}), intermolecular free length (L_f), relaxation time (τ) and attenuation coefficient (α/f^2) were measured for various nanofluids at three different temperatures using ultrasonic velocity, density and viscosity data obtained through the experiments. Adiabatic compressibility of the samples was calculated from the speed of sound (U) and the density of the medium (ρ) using the Newton Laplace relation^{15,16}

$$\beta_{ad} = 1/U^2\rho \quad (1)$$

The intermolecular free length was calculated using the following formula given by Jacobson^{17,18}

$$L_f = K_T \beta_{ad}^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

where, K_T is Jacobson's constant.

The relaxation time (τ) can be calculated from the relation

$$\tau = (4/3) \beta_{ad} \eta \quad (3)$$

Attenuation coefficient was evaluated from the values of ultrasonic velocity and relaxation time by using Stokes relation¹⁹

$$\alpha/f^2 = 4\pi^2\tau/2U \quad (4)$$

Parameters like ultrasonic velocity, density and viscosity of nanofluids of various concentrations at three different temperatures are listed in Table 1 and Fig. 5, Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 respectively whereas adiabatic compressibility, intermolecular free length, relaxation time and attenuation coefficient are tabulated in Table 2 and Fig. 8, Fig. 9, Fig. 10 and Fig. 11 respectively.

From the data recorded in these tables, it has been

Fig. 4. EDAX spectrum of Al₂O₃ nanoparticles.

Table 1. Ultrasonic velocity (*U*), density (ρ) and viscosity (η) of nanofluids having different concentrations of Al₂O₃ in 10% aqueous hexylene glycol at three different temperatures

Temp. (K)	Conc. (wt%)	$U \times 10^{-3}$ (m/s)	$\rho \times 10^{-3}$ (kg m ⁻³)	$\eta \times 10^3$ (kg m ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)
303.15	0	1.56636	0.99504	1.09244
	0.02	1.56788	0.99517	1.11285
	0.04	1.56859	0.99533	1.11809
	0.06	1.56788	0.99550	1.11202
	0.08	1.56727	0.99559	1.10868
	0.10	1.56806	0.99579	1.11228
308.15	0	1.57364	0.99320	0.97825
	0.02	1.57518	0.99333	0.99325
	0.04	1.57605	0.99350	0.99784
	0.06	1.57549	0.99367	0.99209
	0.08	1.57469	0.99376	0.98917
	0.10	1.57543	0.99395	0.99903
313.15	0	1.58091	0.99116	0.86290
	0.02	1.58227	0.99129	0.88080
	0.04	1.58315	0.99145	0.89343
	0.06	1.58202	0.99164	0.88873
	0.08	1.58137	0.99174	0.88501
	0.10	1.58245	0.99192	0.89506

observed that there occurs an increase in ultrasonic velocity and viscosity upto some concentration of Al₂O₃ nanoparticles after that their values start decreasing and finally a little increase occurs in their values. The increase in ultrasonic velocity and viscosity at lower concentration of Al₂O₃ nanoparticles is due to intermolecular hydrogen bonding among Al₂O₃ nanoparticles, hexylene

Fig. 5. Plots of ultrasonic velocity of various nanofluids of Al₂O₃ in 10% aqueous hexylene glycol at different temperatures.

Fig. 6. Plots of density of various nanofluids of Al₂O₃ in 10% aqueous hexylene glycol at different temperatures.

Fig. 7. Plots of viscosity of various nanofluids of Al₂O₃ in 10% aqueous hexylene glycol at different temperatures.

sibility of the medium increases and hence ultrasonic velocity and viscosity decreases. At some higher concentration of Al₂O₃ nanoparticles they start aggregating due to inter particle interactions and hence their interactions with glycol and water molecules decreasing which in turn increasing the hydrogen bonding between glycol and water molecules and hence a little increase occurs in the values of ultrasonic velocity and viscosity. The variation of ultrasonic velocity in any solution depends upon the increase or decrease of intermolecular free lengths after mixing the component. As the free length decreases due to the increase in concentrations of Al₂O₃ nanoparticles upto some concentration, ultrasonic velocity increases, it indicates significant interactions between the solute-solvent molecules suggesting a structure promoting tendency of the added solute. But at some higher concentration of

Table 2. Adiabatic compressibility (β_{ad}), intermolecular free length (L_f), relaxation time (τ), and attenuation coefficient (α/f^2) of nanofluids having different concentrations of Al₂O₃ in 10% aqueous hexylene glycol at three different temperatures

Temp. (K)	Conc. (wt%)	$\beta_{ad} \times 10^{10}$ (m kg ⁻¹ s)	$L_f \times 10^{11}$ (m)	$\tau \times 10^{13}$ (s)	$\alpha/f^2 \times 10^{-14}$ (s ² m ⁻¹)
303.15	0	4.09614	4.19957	5.96637	7.51115
	0.02	4.08769	4.19524	6.06531	7.62833
	0.04	4.08331	4.19300	6.08735	7.65258
	0.06	4.08632	4.19454	6.05876	7.62010
	0.08	4.08914	4.19598	6.04473	7.60539
	0.10	4.08419	4.19345	6.05702	7.61703
308.15	0	4.06586	4.22183	5.30322	6.64545
	0.02	4.05737	4.21742	5.37331	6.72668
	0.04	4.05223	4.21475	5.39130	6.74548
	0.06	4.05438	4.21587	5.36308	6.71256
	0.08	4.05814	4.21782	5.35225	6.70240
	0.10	4.05355	4.21544	5.39950	6.75839
313.15	0	4.03685	4.24442	4.64453	5.79328
	0.02	4.02935	4.24047	4.73207	5.89738
	0.04	4.02423	4.23778	4.79383	5.97104
	0.06	4.02921	4.24040	4.77451	5.95122
	0.08	4.03211	4.24192	4.75792	5.93297
	0.10	4.02592	4.23866	4.80458	5.98708

glycol and water molecules as a result of this bonding overall compressibility of the medium decreases and hence ultrasonic velocity and viscosity increases. But above a particular concentration of Al₂O₃ nanoparticles their interactions with glycol and water molecules increases which in turn start decreasing the hydrogen bonding between glycol and water molecules as a result overall compress-

ibility of the medium increases and hence ultrasonic velocity and viscosity decreases. At some higher concentration of nanoparticles due to inter particle interactions the glycol water interactions increases indicated by decrease in intermolecular free length and increase in ultrasonic velocity. Density shows an increase with in-

Fig. 8. Plots of adiabatic compressibility of various nanofluids of Al_2O_3 in 10% aqueous hexylene glycol at different temperatures.

Fig. 9. Plots of intermolecular free length of various nanofluids of Al_2O_3 in 10% aqueous hexylene glycol at different temperatures.

crease in concentration of nanoparticles. Adiabatic compressibility also shows the same trend as that of intermolecular free length with increase in concentration of nanoparticles. The trends of variation of relaxation time and attenuation coefficient with increase in concentration of nanoparticles are same as that of ultrasonic velocity and viscosity.

Conclusion

Al_2O_3 nanoparticles were dispersed in base fluid a 10% aqueous solution of hexylene glycol with the help of ultrasonicator. Ultrasonic velocity, density, viscosity, re-

Fig. 10. Plots of relaxation time of various nanofluids of Al_2O_3 in 10% aqueous hexylene glycol at different temperatures.

Fig. 11. Plots of attenuation coefficient of various nanofluids of Al_2O_3 in 10% aqueous hexylene glycol at different temperatures.

laxation time and attenuation coefficient showed an increase with increase in concentration of Al_2O_3 nanoparticles upto 0.04 wt% after that these parameters showed a decrease with increase in concentration of Al_2O_3 nanoparticles upto 0.08 wt% on further increasing the concentration these parameters start increasing while adiabatic compressibility and intermolecular free length showed an opposite trend with increase in concentration of Al_2O_3 nanoparticles. It has also been observed that with rise in temperature there occurs an increase in ultrasonic velocity and intermolecular free length while density, viscosity, adiabatic

compressibility, relaxation time and attenuation coefficient showed a decrease with rise in temperature.

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